

4-Chloro-2, 5-Dimethoxyacetoacetanilide as a Gravimetric Reagent for Beryllium (II) and Copper (II)*

A. M. HUNDEKAR, P. UMAPATHY and D. N. SEN

National Chemical Laboratory, Poona-8.

Manuscript received 1 June 1974 ; accepted 30 September 1974.

4-Chloro-2, 5-dimethoxyacetoacetanilide, has been found to precipitate Be(II) and Cu(II) ions from solutions, quantitatively in the pH range 5.8-6.5 and at slightly higher pHs. The precipitated complexes, having the compositions, $\text{Be}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{NCl})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{NCl})_2$, are stable and can be weighed directly after drying at $115^\circ\text{-}20^\circ$. A method for the estimation of these metal ions, using 4-chloro-2, 5-dimethoxyacetoacetanilide as a precipitant has been described. Beryllium (II) in presence of aluminium (III) and iron (III) and copper (II) in presence of aluminium (III), cadmium (II) and zinc (II) can be precipitated from solutions by masking the foreign ions with disodium salt of EDTA or ammonium fluoride. T. G. A. and D. T. A. data for the beryllium and copper complexes are also presented.

ONLY recently organic precipitating agents for the gravimetric determination of beryllium have been proposed.^{1,2} These reagents form precipitates of definite composition with beryllium so that the precipitates can be weighed directly after drying to constant weight. Although beryllium(II) ion does not react with ligands, such as, 8-quinolinol and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid³, with β -diketones, it forms stable chelates. Ligands containing 1, 3-diketo group have been employed as reagents for beryllium(II) and zirconium (IV) in extraction procedures^{3,4} and for the determination of copper(II)⁵. Thenoyl trifluoroacetone, a substituted β -diketone, was investigated as a complexing agent for the separation and purification of various metallic ions.^{6,7} Since only a few β -diketones were investigated as analytical reagents, particularly for beryllium, 4-chloro-2, 5-dimethoxyacetoacetanilide was examined as a possible organic precipitant for beryllium (II) as well as copper (II) and their separations from other metal ions. The results of our investigation are presented here.

Materials and Methods

Beryllium stock solution was prepared from beryllium nitrate trihydrate, $\text{Be}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or from beryllium hydroxide (Fluka AG., Chemische Fabrik, Buchs, S. G.). The latter was dissolved in nitric acid or hydrochloric acid and was diluted with water. The beryllium content was determined according to the standard procedure gravimetrically as BeO^8 . Copper sulphate pentahydrate, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (ANALAR) was dissolved in water with a few drops of sulphuric acid. The metal content was determined according to the standard procedure volumetrically⁹. All the other reagents used were of A. R. grade.

4-Chloro-2, 5-dimethoxyacetoacetanilide was prepared from 4-chloro-2, 5-dimethoxyaniline (Fluka AG.) and ethylacetoacetate in presence of small quantities of

triethanolamine following a procedure similar to the one described for the synthesis of acetoacet-o-chloroaniline.¹⁰ Yield, 90%. m. p., $122^\circ\text{-}3^\circ$. Anal. Found: C, 53.60; H, 5.07; N, 5.74; Cl, 13.1%. M^+ , 271. Required for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{NCl}$: C, 53.04; H, 5.19; N, 5.16; Cl, 13.05% M^+ , 271.

I. R(Nujol), 3310 (m, bonded NH), 1710 (vs, C=Ostr.) 1650 (vs, Amide I), 1600 (s, C=C), 1520 (s, Amide II), 1340 (m, Amide III), cm^{-1} ; n. m. r. (CDCl_3), $\tau=7.75$ (CH_3), 3.3 ($>\text{CH}_2$), 6.32 ($-\text{OCH}_3$), 6.17 ($-\text{OCH}_3$), 5 ($=\text{CH}$), 3.5 (3H) 1.67 (6H), 0.39 (NH), -3.5 (OH) (disappeared on D_2O exchange).

Reagent Solution :

1 g. of 4-chloro-2, 5-dimethoxyacetoacetanilide was dissolved in 50 ml. of hot alcohol and was diluted with water to 100 ml. The hot clear (filtered if necessary) 1:1 alcoholic solution was used for the precipitation of beryllium or copper.

Infrared spectrum was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, model 221, equipped with sodium chloride optics. The n. m. r. spectrum was recorded on a Varian Associates, Model, T-60 spectrometer, operating at 60 Mc/s with TMS as internal standard. The mass spectrum was recorded on CEC 21-110B (USA) double focussing mass spectrometer at a voltage of 70 eV and a current of 20 milliamperes.

pH measurements were made with ELICO pH meter, model LI-10. The thermogravimetric and differential thermal analyses were carried out in a Pt-crucible in a MOM Budapest derivatograph at the heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$. in a flowing air atmosphere.

* N. C. L. Communication No. 1861

Procedure for the estimation of beryllium : 10 ml. of the standard beryllium solution containing approximately 10 mg. was pipetted into a 250 ml. beaker, diluted to about 100 ml. with water and heated on a water-bath. To the hot solution 80 ml of hot ligand solution or the required quantity (a slight excess was used) was added with stirring. The pH of the resulting clear solution was adjusted by the careful drop wise addition of dilute ammonia (1:4), with stirring, until neutral to methyl red indicator (pH papers may also be used). The addition of ammonia was stopped when the red colour of the indicator just disappeared (pH ~ 6.0 - 6.2). The final volume at this stage should be about 200 ml. The bulky white crystalline precipitate formed, settled down, on digestion for 1 hr., on the water-bath leaving a clear supernatant liquid. The precipitated complex was collected on a weighed sintered glass crucible (porosity No. 3 or 4), while hot, washed with boiling water first (~ 200 ml) and then with 1:1 cold aqueous alcohol (30-40 ml). The crucible was dried at 115°-20° for 2 hr. cooled in a desiccator and weighed as $\text{Be}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{NCl})_2$. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF BERYLLIUM USING 4-CHLORO-2, 5-DIMETHOXY ACETOACETANILIDE AS A REAGENT.

Be taken (mg)	Be found (mg)	Error
3.8	3.75	-0.05
8.6	8.62	+0.02
	8.60	-
9.5	9.53	+0.03
	9.50	-

Procedure for the estimation of beryllium in presence of Al^{+++} and Fe^{+++} .

The procedure adopted was the same as above except that, when the foreign ions were present (~ 50 mg.) 0.5 - 1.0 g. of disodium salt of EDTA, was added to mask Al^{+++} or Fe^{+++} and the beryllium complex was precipitated with ammonia (1:4), with stirring. The solution was neutral to methyl red or slightly above (pH 6.5.) The results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF BERYLLIUM FROM FOREIGN IONS

Be taken (mg.)	Foreign ion added (mg.)	Be found (mg.)
7.8	-	7.85
7.8	10(Al^{+++})	7.85
7.8	25(Al^{+++})	7.8
7.8	50(Al^{+++})	7.78
7.8	10(Fe^{+++})	7.8
7.8	25(Fe^{+++})	7.8
7.8	50(Fe^{+++})	7.89

Procedure for the estimation of copper : An aliquot of the standard copper solution was pipetted into a 250 ml. beaker, diluted to about 100 ml and heated on a water-bath. To the hot solution was added

~ 80 ml of the hot 1:1 alcoholic solution of 4-chloro-2, 5-dimethoxyacetoacetanilide, with stirring. To the resulting clear solution dilute ammonia (1:4) was added drop-wise, with stirring, until the precipitation was complete (methyl red indicator was used). The final volume was adjusted to about 200 ml. The precipitated green complex, on digestion for 1 hr. on the water-bath, settled down. The complex was collected, while hot, on a weighed sintered glass crucible (porosity No. 3 or 4), washed with boiling water (200 ml.) first and then with cold alcohol (30-40 ml), dried at 115°-20° for 2 hr., and weighed as $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{NCl})_2$. Results of the estimations are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF COPPER USING 4-CHLORO-2, 5-DIMETHOXY-ACETOACETANILIDE AS A REAGENT

Cu taken (mg.)	Cu found (mg.)	Error
4.63	4.62	-0.01
9.24	9.24	-
18.98	19.0	+0.02
23.72	23.9	+0.08
	23.7	-0.02

Procedure for the estimation of copper in presence of Al^{+++} , Cd^{++} and Zn^{++}

The procedure adopted was the same as above except that in the presence of foreign ions (50 mg.) 0.5 to 1.0 g. of solid ammonium fluoride was added and copper was precipitated with dilute ammonia. (the solution was neutral to methyl red indicator or slightly above pH 6.85). Results of the estimations are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—SEPARATION OF COPPER FROM FOREIGN IONS

Cu taken (mg)	Foreign ion added (mg.)	Cu found (mg.)
9.1	-	9.05
9.1	10 (Zn^{++})	9.07
9.1	25 (Zn^{++})	8.98
9.1	50 (Zn^{++})	9.20
9.1	5 (Al^{+++})	9.08
9.1	10 (Al^{+++})	9.09
9.1	20 (Al^{+++})	9.08
9.1	5 (Cd^{++})	9.20
9.1	10 (Cd^{++})	8.98
9.1	20 (Cd^{++})	8.98

Composition of the precipitate : The precipitated beryllium complex obtained, in the above manner was collected, washed and dried at 115°-20° and was analysed for nitrogen and beryllium. Found : Be, 1.60 ; N, 5.11. Calcd. for $\text{Be}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{NCl})_2$: Be, 1.64 ; N, 5.09%.

Similarly the precipitated pale green copper complex was analysed for nitrogen and copper. Found : Cu, 10.4 ; N, 4.7 ; Calcd. for $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{NCl})_2$: Cu, 10.52 ; N, 4.63%.

The influence of pH as well as that of the concentration of the reagent on precipitation were studied employing 10 ml of standard beryllium (II) or copper (II) solutions. Varying quantities of dilute ammonia or ligand solution were used for precipitation. These studies revealed that the pH range of quantitative precipitation for beryllium was 5.8-6.5 ; for copper the pH range was 6.0-7.3, and that a slight excess of the reagent (~ 5%) should be present. Addition of undue excess of the reagent solution might present difficulties during washing and should be avoided.

Results and Discussion

4-Chloro-2, 5-dimethoxyacetoacetanilide has been found to precipitate from solutions, beryllium (II) ion quantitatively in the pH range 5.8-6.5. The precipitated bulky complex having the composition $\text{Be}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{NCl})_2$ was found to be insoluble in the medium and could be washed free from any excess ligand with boiling water and small quantities of 1:1 alcohol. It is thermally stable, could be dried at 115°-20° and weighed directly. The method is particularly suitable for the estimation of small quantities of beryllium (3 to 10 mg.). Higher quantities were found to result in unwieldy precipitate and transferring this completely to the sintered glass crucible, normally available, may become difficult. Beryllium was separated from Al^{+++} and Fe^{+++} , in presence of sodium salt of EDTA. It was observed that better results were obtained when the pH of the solution was raised to 6.5.

Copper (II) ion could be precipitated from solution, quantitatively in the pH range 6.0-7.3. The presence of EDTA completely prevented the precipitation of copper. For separating copper from Cd^{++} , Zn^{++} and Al^{+++} , ammonium fluoride was used as a sequestering agent. Fe^{+++} , however interfered seriously with the estimation of copper.

Thermogravimetric and differential thermal analyses were carried out to study the decomposition processes of the precipitated complexes of beryllium (II) and copper (II) with 4-chloro-2, 5-dimethoxyacetoacetanilide. According to the data from TG and DTA analyses (Figs. 1 and 2) the complexes were quite stable thermally upto 220°-240°. Decomposition started only from this temperature region onwards and accelerated weight loss for the complexes occurred in the temperature region 400°-600°. Broad and pronounced exothermic peaks with maxima at 540° and 520° for beryllium (II) and copper (II) complexes respectively were observed in the DTA curves. The initial endothermic peaks observed at about 270° for both the compounds may be due to the combined effects of melting and loss of the organic part of the compounds. The small but visible inflection (unresolved endothermic peak) observed for the beryllium complex at 400° in the DTA curve preceding the rapid decomposition process could be due to the loss of a ligand molecule initially (theoretical 49.37% ; found : 49%), with the formation of an apparently unstable monovalent beryllium complex. A

Fig. 1. T.G.A. & D.T.A. Curves for the Beryllium (II) Complex of 4-Chloro-2,5-Dimethoxy Acetoacetanilide. (Amount taken, 200 mg. T denotes the temperature of the sample as a function of time represented by abscissa. D.T.A. sensitivity, $\frac{1}{10}$).

Fig. 2. T.G.A. & D.T.A. Curves for the Copper (II) Complex of 4-Chloro-2, 5-Dimethoxy Acetoacetanilide.

small but noticeable endothermic peak was also observed for the copper complex at 360°. The mass spectral studies on several beryllium chelates with β diketones revealed that upon electron impact, the beryllium chelates break-down in a well-defined manner leading to changes in metal valency.^{1,2} The existence of beryllium (I) ion under certain conditions (as a product of anodic oxidation) also was previously reported.^{1,2}

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to Miss. N. D. Dhanasree for the help in recording TGA and DTA curves.

References

1. J. DAS and S.C. SHOME., *Anal. Chim. Acta. (Amsterdam)*, 1961, **24**, 37.
2. J. DAS and S. BANERJEE., *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1961, **184**, 110 ; 1962, **188**, 109.
3. R. A. BOLOMEY and L. WISH., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4483.
4. E. H. HUFFMAN and L. J. BEAUFAIT., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3179.
5. A. K. SARKAR and J. DAS., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 507.
6. M. CALVIN and E. L. ZEBROSKI., *Atomic Energy Commission Report*. 1947, MDDC-1405.
7. R. A. BOLOMEY and L. WISH., *Atomic Energy Commission Report*, 1948, ORNL-136.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text-Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis" Longmans Green and Co. Ltd., London, p. 517.
9. A. I. VOGEL., "A Text-Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green and Co. Ltd., London, p. 358.
10. B.I.O.S. Final Report No. 986, Part I, p. 22.
11. S. K. BHASIN, P. UMAPATHY and D. N. SEN., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 1113.
12. B. D. LAUGHLIN, J. KLEINBERG and A. W. DAVIDSON., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 559.